

Summary Report of the Nantucket Spider Biodiversity Inventory

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Abstract

We collected spiders on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands in 2006 and 2007 to assemble a list of species for the area. While most identifications have not been verified, the current list represents 301 species. Identification work is ongoing. We have a measure of capture effort associated with 96 % of the 3,762 specimens and all the data are stored in an Access database at the Maria Mitchell Natural Science Museum. 17% of the specimens have been deposited at the Museum of Comparative Zoology in Cambridge, MA. The current collection is 47% similar to a historical species list published by James Emerton in 1930. We located the voucher collection Emerton left with the Maria Mitchell Association in 1930 and we hope to re-identify many of his specimens. In this document we report our 2007 collecting efforts, summarize the state of the collection, provide species lists for the three islands and seven Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative 10 hectare plots.

Background

Over the last two years, with support from the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) and the Maria Mitchell Association (MMA) we have compiled a list of over over 221 spider species on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget and assembled lists for five main habitats on the islands. Most of the common island species are represented in the collection and the current database is set up in such a way that casual spider collections and donations to the MMA Natural Science Museum can continue indefinitely.

The goals of this project continue to direct our current efforts and they include:

- 1) Create a list of the spiders of Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget and compare it to a historical list produced in 1930 (Emerton 1930)
- 2) Create species lists for established biodiversity plots representing Nantucket's major habitats.
- 3) Use outreach programs both to educate the public about spiders and to collect specimens.
- 4) Re-identify the 1930 Emerton collection using current classification schemes.
- 5) Deposit specimens at the Museum for Comparative Zoology (MCZ) and deposit a voucher collection at the MMA Natural Science Museum.

The purpose of this report is to update the report of our activities 2006 activities (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2007), report on our general collecting in 2007 and summarize the results of all our projects.

Caveat: Many of the species identifications reported here have not yet been verified and some may change as the collection is checked for errors.

Collection Activities 2007

Nantucket

We continued to collect spiders to update the island species list and try to find the 172 species listed by James Emerton in 1930 (two of which were left unidentified by him) (Emerton 1930). Emerton personally collected many of his specimens along marshes and pond shores whereas in 2006, we focused on interior island habitats. Because of this, we only collected 72 species from his list by October 2006. For 2007, our goal was to increase this number. Along with scientific collecting (See Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2008a) this involved several hours of casual collecting and four public collection trips to four different areas: the University of Massachusetts Field Station, the Creeks NBI plot, the Nantucket Conservation Foundation (NCF) property on Madaket Road with the large bamboo stand, and an area on Tuckernuck Island.

These casual collections added 20 identified species and 13 unidentified species. Of the former, eight species matched with Emerton's list. More scientifically rigorous collecting projects added 18 identified species and 12 unidentified species. Four of the former matched with Emerton.

A list of species that we have collected but are not on Emerton's list is in Appendix N. Many of these are probable Nantucket County records. Voucher specimens need to be verified before we can confidentially determine this.

The Emerton Collection

Emerton was an eminent arachnologist at the turn of the 20th century and he collected 172 spider species on Nantucket in 1928 and 1929 (Emerton 1930). As far as we can tell, he deposited a voucher collection at MMA and the rest of the collection at the MCZ. The MMA voucher collection became extremely desiccated over the next half century and in the early 1990's Tom Chase, an Eastern Massachusetts Programs Director for the Nature Conservancy on Martha's Vineyard, found the collection while visiting Nantucket and began re-hydrating it. He was able to put about half of the collection through a rehydration process so that the specimens were once again safely stored in 70% ethanol. The other half of the collection was completely dried out and too fragile to work with. Much credit goes to Chase for saving the collection which is not only scientifically important but historically important as well.

Since Emerton's time, many spider species names have been synonymized or split. We could find no modern name for five of his species and two of his species he left unidentified. To accurately compare our current collection with his historical one, we needed to look at his specimens. In July 2007, an MMA intern travelled to Martha's Vineyard to pick up the collection from Chase. In August we delivered the collection to the MCZ to be catalogued by Laura Leibensperger. Leibensperger may also try to re-hydrate more of the specimens.

We will compare the historical and modern collections more closely after identifications in both are more stabilized. They are 47% similar in their current states (Sorenson similarity). There are 92 species shared and 78 species different between the two. Twenty-three of the latter are in the difficult family Linyphiidae and our collection contains 48 unidentified Linyphiidae species many of which may overlap with Emerton's. We are currently focusing on the identification of these spiders and will have most of them tentatively identified by the summer 2008.

Continuation of collections on Tuckernuck Island

We completed a three day collecting trip to Tuckernuck from 29-31 July 2007 to run a public spider education program, collect spiders to update the island's species list, search specifically for reported black widows (*Latrodectus variolus*) and revisit the *Sphodros rufipes* colonies (Atypidae, puresweb spiders) in hopes of finding *Sphodros niger* webs as well (See Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2008b).

We added 26 species to the list for a total of 81 species (Appendix D). Forty-six of these are represented by only one specimen and 20 are identified only to genus or family. Of the latter, 11 are in the complicated family, Linyphiidae, and will be identified by May 2008. These collections added two possible county records: *Drassodes robinsoni* (Gnaphosidae) and the *Tibellus duttoni* (Philodromidae). Eight of the species have not been found on Nantucket.

The Northern Black Widow

Northern Black Widows, *Latrodectus variolus* (Walckenaer), from Tuckernuck have not been conclusively shown to be genetically identical to specimens from Martha's Vineyard but they are believed to be the same (Tom Chase and Herb Levi, pers. comm. summer 2007). However, preliminary observations suggest that they show distinctly different behaviors concerning social interactions between adult females. The spiders seem to be very tolerant of each other and we observed several captive females enter their neighbor's web, perform what we assume are communication behaviors (e.g. vibrating the abdomen), and then leave unscathed. This is very unusual and has not been reported before (Herb Levi, pers. comm. summer 2007). On Tuckernuck, the webs can be very close together and in a survey of a 25m x 25m plot of sandplain grassland we recorded 25 *Latrodectus* webs with an average distance to the nearest neighbor of 2.1 ± 0.06 m. We do not know whether this close proximity increases social interaction and it may be that these groups of webs are siblings radiating from one central 'mother' web.

We collected three adult and six immature specimens of *L. variolus*, mostly from the east side of the island. These spiders build webs in grasses and low vegetation using very fine silk. We found the highest densities of webs in sandplain grassland areas east of the Tuckernuck Field Station but we also located webs in the oak forests to the west of the station. All observed female spiders hid in a retreat built inside the base of a grass tuft or in some other cavity (e.g. a rotting log) and the rest of the web extended vertically up the vegetation and then spread horizontally to nearby vegetation. We came across several webs with *Latrodectus* hatchlings moving out across these horizontal portions to nearby grass tufts.

We also observed that all the spiders in retreats under vegetation or underground were in close proximity to an unidentified species of ant. Spiders in the family Theridiidae have been well documented as ant predators (Holldobler 1970; Porter and Eastman 1981) and the Western Widow spider (*Latrodectus hesperus*) has been shown to significantly influence the behaviors of harvester ants in California (MacKay 1982). However, individuals of *L. hesperus* only approached ants trapped in a web and we have observed *L. variolus* in close contact with ants. Captive immature *L. variolus* feed very well on ants in the lab and they may be an important food source for the spider on Tuckernuck. Detailed study of this interaction is needed.

Current Collection Status

Over two years we have collected 3,762 spiders from all three islands representing 301 possible species (78 species are unidentified) (Table 1). Specimens have been collected in over 28 areas between the three islands (Fig. 1). Of this total, 2,332 specimens (adults and immatures) have been tentatively identified (Appendix B). In 2007, 639 identified spiders representing 84 species were deposited at the MCZ. Remaining at the MMA are 462 adult spiders that represent the 202 species of the voucher collection for the 2006 field season. Seventy of these remain unidentified or the identification is unsure but they will eventually be deposited at the MCZ.

We collected an additional 882 specimens in 2007 representing 132 species that have been incorporated into the collection. While most of the species still need to be verified, only 25 are unidentified. Altogether there are 1,344 adults (882+462) stored at the MMA. There are also 1,779 immature spiders stored at the MMA and all of the specimens are geo-referenced. This is a total of 3,123 spiders. The MMA will store the immatures and a voucher collection of roughly 400 of the adults and the rest of the adults will be deposited at the MCZ.

Table 1. Summary of the current spider biodiversity collection.

Year	Stage	# of specimens	Total # of species	# unidentified species
2006	Adult	1,142	202	57
	Immature	1,779	-	-
2007	Adult	882	132	25
	Immature	-	-	-
Total		3,762	301	78
Totals by location				
MMA		3,123	296	78
MCZ		639	84	0

We were not able to organize another collecting trip to Muskeget Island and the species list remains at 32 species (Appendix E). We have started lists for seven of the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) plots including The Creeks, Eel Point 2, Madequecham, Mass. Audubon, Sheep Pond, Smooth Hummocks Coastal Preserve, and Squam Swamp (Appendices F-L). We also have a list for the University of Massachusetts Field Station (Appendix M).

Figure 1. The general areas on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget where we have collected spiders since 2006. Points represent the approximate location where two or more specimens were collected.

Nantucket Spider Database

All the data collected over the life of this project are stored in an Access database at the MMA Natural Science Museum. Directions for its use are in Appendix A. The database is searchable and contains a loan system so that specimens can be shared with the scientific community. It provides the exact location of specimens stored at the MMA.

Electronic Field Guide to the Spiders of Nantucket

Work on this project continues. We have assembled a collection of pictures (of species appearance and close up identification characters) for many of the common species on Nantucket. We are working on constructing the website and hope to provide an online key for the 20 most commonly encountered species.

Discussion

The total number of species is likely to decrease as we work through the unidentified species. However, we still have not found all of the species Emerton captured and we estimate that the actual number of species on the islands is at least 301 and probably more. As we

identify all the Linyphiidae species and re-examine Emerton's specimens, the similarity between the lists will increase significantly.

The collection should in no way be considered complete. The overall sampling intensity (#of adult specimens/# of species) for the islands is seven (2024/301) and to be confident in a complete survey of just one habitat, this number should, at the very least, be 10 (Coddington *et al.* 1991). Most intensive spider surveys that focus on one habitat and aim for a nearly complete species list end up with 30% of the species represented by only one specimen, referred to as singletons (Coddington *et al.* 2007). Our collection is comprised of 40% singletons. We expected this low sampling intensity and high number of singletons since we have collected from multiple habitats over a very large area.

A major success of this project was our dependence on the efforts of many dedicated volunteer collectors and public collecting events. Over the course of the project we have had 43 people volunteer for intensive collections around the island and in biodiversity plots. Public collecting events were important because they not only allowed us to introduce people to the world of arthropods, teach them about the importance of spiders and show them the basics of spider identification, but these events also provided 65 of the 301 species. We estimate that 60 adults and children have attended at least one of the events over the last two years. While it does not approach the complexity and completeness of much larger surveys in Colorado and Ohio, this is an example of completely inexperienced and amateur collectors working together successfully to compile a species list of a difficult taxonomic group for a very large area (Colorado Spider Survey 2005; Ohio Spider Survey 2001). The project is indebted to the Nantucket community.

Future Work

We continue to collect species and accept donated specimens from anywhere on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget. Goals for the 2008 field season include investigating the *L. variolus* population on Tuckernuck, a detailed study of the *S. niger* and *S. rufipes* populations on Nantucket and Tuckernuck, and an investigation into how management strategies in sandplain grassland and heathland affect spider populations. All of these projects build off work reported in this document.

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most of the spiders and our dataset would be considerably smaller without their help: Marcia Augiar, Craig Biegler, Susan Bohem, Jason Bridges, Rob Carr, Ara Charder, Rachel Dacks, Sarah Hinman, Craig Jackson, Diane and Jesse Lang, Dave Martini, Jon, Krysti and Stavros Papandopoulos, Lou Perottii, Caroline Polgar, Rachel Rasfeld, David Ryan, Majorie Thomas, and Darcie Vallant among many others.

Literature Cited

- Coddington, J.A., C. Griswald, D. Davila, E. Penaranda, & S. Larcher. 1991. Designing and testing sampling protocols to estimate biodiversity in tropical systems. Pp. 44-46, *In* The Unity of Evolutionary Biology, Vol. 1. (E. Dudley, ed.). Proc. Fourth Intern. Congr. Syst. Evol. Biol., Dioscorides Press, Portland, Oregon.
- Codington, J.A., I. Agnarsson, M. Kunter, J.A. Miller, and G. Hormiga. 2007. Undersampling bias: the null hypothesis for singleton species in tropical arthropod surveys. Presented annual meeting of the American Arachnological Society. Susquehanna July 13 2007 to July 17, 2007
- Colorado Spider Survey. 2005. Denver Museum of Nature and Science. <http://www.dmns.org/spiders/default.aspx>
- Emerton, J. H. 1930. Spiders of Nantucket. Pp. 161-172. *In* Johnson, C.W. 1930. A list of the insect fauna of Nantucket, Massachusetts. Publ. Nantucket Maria Mitchell Association 3(2):1-174, i-xviii.
- Holldobler, B. 1970. *Steatoda fulva* (Theridiidae), a spider that feeds on harvester ants. *Psyche* 77(2): 202-208
- MacKay, W.P. 1982. The effect of predation of western widow spiders (Araneae: Theridiidae) on harvester ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Oecologia* (Berl) 53:406-411
- Mckenna-Foster. A. and C.B. Beaton. 2007. The Biodiversity and Distribution of Spiders on Nantucket Island, MA. Report submitted to the Nantucket Biodiversity.
- Mckenna-Foster. A. and C.B. Beaton. 2008a. The summer assemblage of spiders in nantucket sandplain grassland and heathland habitat. Report submitted to the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative March 3, 2008.
- Mckenna-Foster. A. and C.B. Beaton. 2008b. 2007 Survey for the purseweb spiders *Sphodros niger* and *Sphodros rufipes*. Report submitted to the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative March 3, 2008.
- Ohio Spider Survey. Bradley, R.A. <http://www.marion.ohio-state.edu/SpiderWeb/OhioSpiderSurvey.htm>
- Porter, S.D. and D.A. Eastmond. 1981. *Euryopsis coki* (Theridiidae), a spider that preys on *Pogonomyrmex* ants. *J. Arachnol.* 10:275-277.

Appendices

Other than Appendix A, all of the following documents list the number of species, specimens, unidentified specimens, and the number of singletons for the Islands, selected Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) plots, and other selected areas. The amount of effort exerted at each NBI plot to catch species is not equal between sites.

Appendix A- Using the MMA Spider Database

Appendix B- Entire species list for Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands.

Appendix C- Nantucket Island species list

Appendix D- Tuckernuck species list

Appendix E- Muskeget species list

Appendix F- The Creeks NBI plot species list

Appendix G- Eel Point 2 NBI plot species list

Appendix H- Madequecham NBI plot species list

Appendix I- Massachusetts Audubon Society NBI plot species list

Appendix J- Sheep Pond NBI plot species list

Appendix K- Smooth Hummocks Coastal Preserve NBI plot species list

Appendix L- Squam Swamp NBI plot species list

Appendix M- University of Massachusetts Field Station species list (area near lab building)

Appendix N- List of species captured in 2006 and 2007 that are not on Emerton's 1930 list.

Appendix A

Using the MMA spider database

This Microsoft Access database keeps track of specimens and allows complex searches and data organization. It is simplified for basic users through a switchboard that is user friendly. Advanced users can manipulate the queries for more intricate searches.

- 1) Open the Access database on the MMA Natural Science Museum collections computer.
- 2) The grey and yellow Main Switchboard box appears presenting several options. You can:
 - a. Search for specimens
 - b. Enter data for new specimens (use this option to change data for specific specimens)
 - c. Search the Museum's library of spider identification material
 - d. Loan a specimen
 - e. Return a loaned specimen
- 3) **Search for Specimens**
 - a. Clicking the grey box next to this option opens a form with a variety of searchable fields.
 - b. You can fill them in using the drop down arrow or by typing directly into the field.
 - c. Access fills in the field if it recognizes the word.
 - d. Click the search button
 - e. Clicking the button at the bottom of the form opens a new window with the search results. You can export this to Excel by clicking on File in the menu bar and selecting Export.
- 4) **Enter New Specimen(s)**
 - a. This option opens the main data entry form for the database.
 - b. From here you navigate through all the records using the vial code (the unique number in each vial). Use the Record Box at the very bottom left of the form to find specific vials.
 - c. After record 311 (vial code 311) the record number is always one less than the vial code (i.e. record 400 is vial code 401). This is due to an error during the database creation.
 - d. From this form you can enter new collection locations and enter new species.
 - e. If you are entering a specimen into the database follow this order:
 - i. Navigate to the empty record at the very end of the database (vial code will be blank).
 - ii. Hit the 'Enter a new location ID' button and a new form will appear. Fill in all the fields and choose a unique alpha-numeric ID (e.g. Casual collection along Straight Warf = STRTWRFcas1. Add a new location if necessary by clicking on the 'Enter new location' button. Same for a new collector- the collector id should be the person's initials but scroll through the records to be sure of no repeats and go to the very last record (it will be empty) to enter data.

- iii. Fill out where the vial will be stored and enter any comments to help locate it.
 - iv. Click the Family field in the 'Specimen table subform' and enter your species information. If the species is not in the database click the 'Enter a new species ID' button. If you identified it put your first initial and last name in the DET field.
 - 1. If you accidentally create a species record that you do not want delete it by right clicking on the little box on the far left of that record and selecting 'delete record'.
 - v. Exit out of the form or push the 'Save and Close' button.
- 5) **Search Reference Library**
- a. This option opens a form with Family and Genus fields.
 - b. Click the drop down arrow for each and select the one you are looking for. You do not have to fill out both.
 - c. The only literature listed is in the museum and most is on one of the shelves near the microscope. Books may be in the MMA science library and some of the files are electronic on the computer.
- 6) **Loan Specimens and Return Loaned Specimens**
- a. Both of these options are straightforward and contain directions within them.
 - b. Access keeps track of what has been loaned and to who and also keeps a basic record of the lending history.

More options may be added and this Appendix will be updated as needed. A copy will be stored next to the collections computer as well as within the MMA Science Library.

Appendix B

Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands

301 species, 78 unidentified, 119 singletons

2,332

specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	22
	Agelenopsis	potteri	4
	Tegenaria	domestica	1
Amaurobiidae	Amaurobius	ferox	5
	Coras	sp. A	1
Anyphaenidae	Arachosia	cubana	1
	Hibana	gracilis	16
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	84
	Araneus	alboventris	1
	Araneus	bicentenarius	2
	Araneus	bivittatus	2
	Araneus	cornutus	5
	Araneus	diadematus	1
	Araneus	gadus	1
	Araneus	marmoreus	1
	Araneus	miniatus	4
	Araneus	partitus	2
	Araneus	pratensis	1
	Araneus	sp. TB	1
	Araneus	thaddeus	3
	Araneus	trifolium	3
	Araniella	displicata	1
	Argiope	aurantia	11
	Argiope	trifasciata	23
	Cyclosa	conica	2
	Cyclosa	turbinata	2
	Eustala	anastera	12
	Eustala	emertoni	2
	Larinia	borealis	1
	Mangora	maculata	4
	Micrathena	sagittata	18
	Neoscona	arabesca	126
	Neoscona	pratensis	17
	No id	sp. A	19
	No id	sp. B	2
	No id	sp. C	4
No id	sp. E	8	
Atypidae	Sphodros	niger	3
	Sphodros	rufipes	24
Clubionidae	Clubiona	abbotii	8
	Clubiona	johnsoni	16
	Clubiona	kastoni	1
	Clubiona	maritima	1

	Clubiona	pikei	11
	Clubiona	sp. A	7
	Elaver	excepta	15
Corinnidae	Castianeira	cingulata	1
	Castianeira	longipalpa	33
	Castianeira	trilineata	2
	Meriola	decepta	5
	Phrurolithus	similis	13
	Phruronellus	formica	13
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	19
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	9
	Phrurotimpus	minutus	18
	Scotinella	divesta	1
	Scotinella	minnetonka	1
	Scotinella	pugnata	1
	Trachelas	pacificus	1
Dictynidae	Cicurina	arcuata	2
	Dictyna	formidolosa	1
	Dictyna	sp. A	23
	Dictyna	sp. B	30
	Emblyna	annulipes	1
	Emblyna	cruciata	11
	Lathys	pallida	7
	No id	sp. A	1
	Scotolathys	pallidus	7
Dysderidae	Dysdera	crocata	3
Gnaphosidae	Callilepis	pluto	1
	Cesonia	bilineata	10
	Drassodes	neglectus	1
	Drassodes	robinsoni	1
	Drassyllus	creolus	29
	Drassyllus	sp. B	1
	Haplodrassus	signifer	57
	Micaria	longispina	2
	Nodocion	eclecticus	1
	Sergiolus	decoratus	6
	Sergiolus	minutus	1
	Zelotes	duplex	19
	Zelotes	fratis	2
	Zelotes	hentzi	28
	Zelotes	laccus	44
Hahniidae	Hahnia	cinerea	1
	Neoantistea	agilis	3
Linyphiidae	Agyneta	sp. A	3
	Agyneta	sp. B	3
	Bathyphantes	pallidus	8
	Bathyphantes	reprobus	1
	Ceraticelus	alticeps	19
	Ceraticelus	bryantae	1
	Ceraticelus	fissiceps	1

Ceraticelus	silus	1
Ceraticelus	sp. TA	34
Ceratinella	sp. A	1
Ceratinops	crenatus	1
Ceratinopsis	atolma	1
Ceratinopsis	nigriceps	1
Ceratinopsis	sp. A	1
Erigone	dentosa	1
Erigone	sp. A	1
Florinda	coccinea	3
Grammonota	capitata	3
Grammonota	inornata	2
Grammonota	maritima	1
Grammonota	pictilis	8
Grammonota	sp. A	1
Grammonota	sp. B	8
Grammonota	sp. C	1
Hypselistes	florens	13
Macrargus	multesimus	5
Maso	sp. A	2
Maso	sp. B	2
Masoncus	arienus	1
Neriene	clathrata	25
No id	sp. A	1
No id	sp. AA	1
No id	sp. AB	1
No id	sp. AC	1
No id	sp. AD	2
No id	sp. AE	2
No id	sp. BA	1
No id	sp. BB	1
No id	sp. BC	1
No id	sp. BD	2
No id	sp. BE	1
No id	sp. BF	1
No id	sp. C	3
No id	sp. D	4
No id	sp. K	1
No id	sp. P	2
No id	sp. R	1
No id	sp. S	3
No id	sp. T	1
No id	sp. TB	1
No id	sp. TC	1
No id	sp. TD	1
No id	sp. TE	1
No id	sp. TF	1
No id	sp. TG	1
No id	sp. TI	1
No id	sp. U	2

	No id	sp. W	2
	No id	sp. WW	2
	No id	sp. X	5
	No id	sp. XX	3
	No id	sp. Y	1
	No id	sp. YY	2
	No id	sp. Z	1
	No id	sp. ZZ	1
	Pocadicnemis	americana	2
	Tennesseellum	formicum	2
	Walckenaeria	atrotibialis	2
	Walckenaeria	digitata	1
	Walckenaeria	sp. A	2
Liocranidae	Agroeca	ornata	1
	Agroeca	pratensis	17
Lycosidae	Allocosa	funerea	6
	Arctosa	emertoni	1
	Arctosa	littoralis	8
	Arctosa	rubicunda	2
	Geolycosa	pikei	24
	Geolycosa	sp. TA	1
	Hogna	aspera	1
	Hogna	carolinensis	2
	Hogna	frondicola	23
	Hogna	helluo	12
	Pardosa	distincta	97
	Pardosa	floridana	4
	Pardosa	milvina	1
	Pardosa	moesta	15
	Pardosa	saxatilis	113
	Pardosa	sp. A	5
	Pirata	cantralli	1
	Pirata	insularis	7
	Pirata	piraticus	1
	Pirata	sedentarius	1
	Rabidosa	punctulata	2
	Rabidosa	rabida	12
	Schizocosa	avida	40
	Schizocosa	bilineata	70
	Schizocosa	ocreata	3
	Schizocosa	saltatrix	3
	Schizocosa	sp. B	1
	Trabeops	aurantiacus	20
	Trebacosa	marxi	8
	Trochosa	ruricola	1
	Trochosa	sp. A	1
	Trochosa	terricola	4
	Varacosa	shenandoa	2
Mimetidae	Mimetus	notius	2
Miturgidae	Cheiracanthium	inclusum	6

	Cheiracanthium	mildei	2
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus	8
	Oxyopes	scalaris	9
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	4
	Philodromus	placidus	14
	Thanatus	formicinus	23
	Tibellus	duttoni	1
	Tibellus	oblongus	15
Pholcidae	Pholcus	phalangioides	16
Pisauridae	Dolmedes	sp. A	2
Salticidae	Admestina	tibialis	1
	Admestina	wheeleri	1
	Eris	militaris	8
	Habronattus	borealis	1
	Habronattus	decorus	1
	Habronattus	sp. A	2
	Habronattus	viridipes	2
	Hentzia	palmarum	63
	Maevia	inclemens	5
	Maevia	vittata	1
	Marpissa	lineata	4
	Marpissa	pikei	3
	Neon	nellii	2
	No id	sp. D	7
	No id	sp. E	3
	Pelegrina	flavipes	7
	Pelegrina	galathea	6
	Pelegrina	proterva	27
	Phidippus	audax	2
	Phidippus	cardinalis	3
	Phidippus	clarus	7
	Phidippus	whitmanii	1
	Platycryptus	undatus	3
	Salticus	scenicus	1
	Synemosyna	formica	4
	Talavera	minuta	5
	Zygoballus	rufipes	12
Scytodidae	Scytodes	thoracica	2
Segestriidae	Ariadna	bicolor	2
Tetragnathidae	Leucauge	venusta	20
	Tetragnatha	caudata	14
	Tetragnatha	elongata	1
	Tetragnatha	guatemalensis	1
	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	26
	Tetragnatha	seneca	1
	Tetragnatha	vermiformis	2
	Tetragnatha	versicolor	1
	Tetragnatha	viridis	12
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	globosa	1
	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	18

	Argyrodes	trigonum	1
	Crustulina	sticta	1
	Dipoena	nigra	1
	Emertonella	emertoni	1
	Emertonella	gertschi	8
	Enoplognatha	ovata	4
	Euryopis	argentea	1
	Euryopis	funnebris	12
	Euryopis	gertschi	31
	Euryopis	sp. A	1
	Euryopis	sp. B	2
	Latrodectus	mactans	1
	Latrodectus	sp. A	3
	Latrodectus	variolus	6
	No id	sp. B	3
	No id	sp. L	1
	No id	sp. N	1
	No id	sp. O	1
	No id	sp. P	1
	No id	sp. TB	1
	No id	sp. TC	5
	Phoroncidia	americana	1
	Robertus	frontatus	1
	Robertus	pumulis	1
	Steatoda	albomaculata	1
	Steatoda	americana	4
	Steatoda	borealis	2
	Steatoda	sp. A	1
	Steatoda	sp. TA	1
	Takayus	lyricus	7
	Theonoe	stridula	1
	Theridion	albidum	6
	Theridion	differens	6
	Theridion	frondeum	1
	Theridion	gluacescens	1
	Theridion	murarium	1
	Thymoites	unimaculatus	11
	Tidarren	sp. TA	2
	Wamba	congener	1
	Wamba	crispulus	1
Thomisidae	Misumena	sp. A	1
	Misumenoides	formosipes	11
	Misumenops	asperatus	1
	Misumenops	oblongus	1
	Ozyptila	americana	37
	Ozyptila	conspurcata	21
	Ozyptila	practicola	1
	Tmarus	rubromaculatus	1
	Xysticus	alboniger	7
	Xysticus	bicuspis	6

Xysticus	ferox	33
Xysticus	fraternus	5
Xysticus	funestus	13
Xysticus	gulosus	3
Xysticus	luctans	28
Xysticus	pellax	2
Xysticus	triguttatus	3

Appendix C

Nantucket Island

265 species, 64 unidentified, 106 singletons

1,903 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens	
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	15	
	Agelenopsis	potteri	4	
	Tegenaria	domestica	1	
Amaurobiidae	Amaurobius	ferox	5	
	Coras	sp. A	1	
Anyphaenidae	Arachosia	cubana	1	
	Hibana	gracilis	15	
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	46	
	Araneus	alboventris	1	
	Araneus	bicentenarius	1	
	Araneus	bivittatus	2	
	Araneus	diadematus	1	
	Araneus	gadus	1	
	Araneus	marmoreus	1	
	Araneus	miniatus	4	
	Araneus	partitus	2	
	Araneus	pratensis	1	
	Araneus	thaddeus	3	
	Araneus	trifolium	2	
	Araniella	displicata	1	
	Argiope	aurantia	10	
	Argiope	trifasciata	20	
	Cyclosa	conica	2	
	Cyclosa	turbinata	2	
	Eustala	anastera	12	
	Eustala	emertoni	1	
	Larinia	borealis	1	
	Mangora	maculata	4	
	Micrathena	sagittata	11	
	Neoscona	arabesca	110	
	No id	sp. A	5	
	No id	sp. B	1	
	No id	sp. C	4	
	No id	sp. E	8	
	Atypidae	Sphodros	niger	3
	Clubionidae	Clubiona	abbotii	8
		Clubiona	johnsoni	16
		Clubiona	kastoni	1
		Clubiona	maritima	1
Clubiona		pikei	3	
Clubiona		sp. A	7	
Elaver		excepta	14	
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	33	
	Castianeira	trilineata	2	

	Meriola	decepta	5
	Phrurolithus	similis	13
	Phruronellus	formica	5
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	16
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	9
	Phrurotimpus	minutus	18
	Scotinella	divesta	1
	Scotinella	minnetonka	1
	Scotinella	pugnata	1
	Trachelas	pacificus	1
Dictynidae	Cicurina	arcuata	1
	Dictyna	formidolosa	1
	Dictyna	sp. A	7
	Dictyna	sp. B	20
	Emblyna	annulipes	1
	Emblyna	cruciata	11
	Lathys	pallida	7
	No id	sp. A	1
	Scotolathys	pallidus	7
Dysderidae	Dysdera	crocata	3
Gnaphosidae	Callilepis	pluto	1
	Cesonia	bilineata	8
	Drassodes	neglectus	1
	Drassyllus	creolus	29
	Drassyllus	sp. B	1
	Haplodrassus	signifer	57
	Micaria	longispina	2
	Nodocion	eclecticus	1
	Sergiolus	capulatus	1
	Sergiolus	decoratus	5
	Sergiolus	minutus	1
	Zelotes	duplex	19
	Zelotes	fratis	2
	Zelotes	hentzi	27
	Zelotes	laccus	44
Hahniidae	Hahnia	cinerea	1
	Neoantistea	agilis	3
Linyphiidae	Agyneta	sp. A	3
	Agyneta	sp. B	3
	Bathyphantes	pallidus	7
	Bathyphantes	reprobus	1
	Ceraticelus	alticeps	13
	Ceraticelus	bryantae	1
	Ceraticelus	sp. TA	1
	Ceratinella	sp. A	1
	Ceratinops	crenatus	1
	Ceratinopsis	atolma	1
	Ceratinopsis	nigriceps	1
	Erigone	dentosa	1
	Erigone	sp. A	1

	Florinda	coccinea	3
	Grammonota	capitata	2
	Grammonota	pictilis	8
	Grammonota	sp. A	1
	Grammonota	sp. B	8
	Hypselistes	florens	10
	Macrargus	multesimus	5
	Maso	sp. A	2
	Maso	sp. B	2
	Masoncus	arienus	1
	Nerienne	clathrata	25
	No id	sp. A	1
	No id	sp. AA	1
	No id	sp. AB	1
	No id	sp. AC	1
	No id	sp. AD	2
	No id	sp. BA	1
	No id	sp. BB	1
	No id	sp. BC	1
	No id	sp. BD	2
	No id	sp. BE	1
	No id	sp. BF	1
	No id	sp. C	1
	No id	sp. D	4
	No id	sp. K	1
	No id	sp. P	2
	No id	sp. R	1
	No id	sp. S	3
	No id	sp. T	1
	No id	sp. U	2
	No id	sp. W	2
	No id	sp. WW	2
	No id	sp. X	4
	No id	sp. XX	3
	No id	sp. Y	1
	No id	sp. YY	2
	No id	sp. Z	1
	No id	sp. ZZ	1
	Pocadicnemis	americana	2
	Tennesseeillum	formicum	2
	Walckenaeria	atrotibialis	2
	Walckenaeria	digitata	1
	Walckenaeria	sp. A	2
Liocranidae	Agroeca	ornata	1
	Agroeca	pratensis	17
Lycosidae	Allocosa	funerea	6
	Arctosa	emertoni	1
	Arctosa	littoralis	1
	Arctosa	rubicunda	2
	Geolycosa	pikei	24

	Hogna	aspera	1
	Hogna	carolinensis	2
	Hogna	frondicola	22
	Hogna	helluo	12
	Pardosa	distincta	93
	Pardosa	floridana	4
	Pardosa	milvina	1
	Pardosa	moesta	15
	Pardosa	saxatilis	113
	Pardosa	sp. A	5
	Pirata	cantralli	1
	Pirata	insularis	5
	Pirata	piraticus	1
	Pirata	sedentarius	1
	Rabidosa	punctulata	2
	Rabidosa	rabida	10
	Schizocosa	avida	37
	Schizocosa	bilineata	70
	Schizocosa	saltatrix	3
	Schizocosa	sp. B	1
	Trabeops	aurantiacus	20
	Trebacosa	marxi	7
	Trochosa	uricola	1
	Trochosa	sp. A	1
	Trochosa	terricola	2
	Varacosa	shenandoa	2
Mimetidae	Mimetus	notius	2
Miturgidae	Cheiracanthium	inclusum	6
	Cheiracanthium	mildei	2
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus	6
	Oxyopes	scalaris	9
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	3
	Philodromus	placidus	13
	Thanatus	formicinus	14
	Tibellus	oblongus	11
Pholcidae	Pholcus	phalangioides	1
Pisauridae	Dolmedes	sp. A	2
Salticidae	Admestina	tibialis	1
	Eris	militaris	8
	Habronattus	borealis	1
	Habronattus	decorus	1
	Habronattus	sp. A	2
	Habronattus	viridipes	2
	Hentzia	palmarum	51
	Maevia	inclemens	4
	Maevia	vittata	1
	Marpissa	lineata	4
	Marpissa	pikei	2
	Neon	nelli	1
	No id	sp. A	1

	No id	sp. D	6
	No id	sp. E	3
	Pelegrina	flavipes	7
	Pelegrina	galathea	5
	Pelegrina	proterva	25
	Phidippus	audax	2
	Phidippus	cardinalis	3
	Phidippus	clarus	6
	Phidippus	whitmanii	1
	Platycryptus	undatus	3
	Synemosyna	formica	4
	Talavera	minuta	4
	Zygoballus	rufipes	7
Scytodidae	Scytodes	thoracica	2
Segestriidae	Ariadna	bicolor	2
Tetragnathidae	Leucauge	venusta	10
	Tetragnatha	caudata	3
	Tetragnatha	elongata	1
	Tetragnatha	guatemalensis	1
	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	19
	Tetragnatha	seneca	1
	Tetragnatha	versicolor	1
	Tetragnatha	viridis	12
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	globosa	1
	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	9
	Argyrodes	trigonum	1
	Emertonella	emertoni	1
	Emertonella	gertschi	8
	Enoplognatha	ovata	4
	Euryopsis	argentea	1
	Euryopsis	funebri	9
	Euryopsis	gertschi	31
	Euryopsis	sp. A	1
	Euryopsis	sp. B	2
	Latrodectus	mactans	1
	No id	sp. B	3
	No id	sp. L	1
	No id	sp. N	1
	No id	sp. O	1
	No id	sp. P	1
	Robertus	pumulis	1
	Steatoda	albomaculata	1
	Steatoda	americana	4
	Steatoda	borealis	1
	Steatoda	sp. A	1
	Takayus	lyricus	5
	Theonoe	stridula	1
	Theridion	albidum	4
	Theridion	differens	6
	Theridion	frondeum	1

	Theridion	murarium	1
	Theridion	spirale	1
	Thymoites	unimaculatus	9
	Wamba	crispulus	1
Thomisidae	Misumena	sp. A	1
	Misumenoides	formosipes	2
	Misumenops	asperatus	1
	Misumenops	oblongus	1
	Ozyptila	americana	37
	Ozyptila	conspurcata	21
	Ozyptila	practicola	1
	Tmarus	rubromaculatus	1
	Xysticus	alboniger	7
	Xysticus	bicuspis	6
	Xysticus	ferox	31
	Xysticus	fraternus	5
	Xysticus	funestus	9
	Xysticus	gulosus	3
	Xysticus	luctans	27
	Xysticus	pellax	2
	Xysticus	triguttatus	1

Appendix D

* indicates species not caught on Nantucket

Tuckernuck Island

81 species, 20 unidentified, 44 singletons

89 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	5
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	20
	Araneus	bicentenarius	1
	Araneus	cornutus	5
	Araneus	Sp. TB	1
	Argiope	aurantia	1
	Argiope	trifasciata	2
	Micrathena	sagittata	7
	Neoscona	arabesca	8
	Neoscona	pratensis	17
	No id	Sp. A, Imm.	14
	No id	Sp. B, Imm.	1
Atypidae	Sphodros	rufipes	24
Clubionidae	Elaver	excepta	1
Corinnidae	Castianeira	cingulata	1
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	3
Dictynidae	Cicurina	arcuata	1
	Dictyna	Sp. A, Imm.	16
	Dictyna	Sp. B, Imm.	10
Gnaphosidae	Cesonia	bilineata	2
	Drassodes	robinsoni*	1
Linyphiidae	Bathypantes	pallidus	1
	Ceraticelus	alticeps	6
	Ceraticelus	fissiceps	1
	Ceraticelus	Sp. TA	33
	Ceraticelus	silus*	1
	Grammonota	capitata	1
	Grammonota	maritima*	1
	No id	Sp. C	2
	No id	Sp. TB	1
	No id	Sp. TC	1
	No id	Sp. TD	1
	No id	Sp. TE	1
	No id	Sp. TF	1
	No id	Sp. TG	1
	No id	Sp. TH	1
	No id	Sp. TI	1
	No id	Sp. X	1
Lycosidae	Geolycosa	Sp. TA	1
	Hogna	frondicola	1
	Pardosa	distincta	4
	Rabidosa	rabida	2
	Schizocosa	avida	2
	Schizocosa	ocreat*	3

	Trebacosa	marxi	1
	Trochosa	terricola	1
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus	2
Philodromidae			
	Philodromus	placidus	1
	Thanatus	formicinus	9
	Tibellus	duttoni*	1
Salticidae	Admestina	wheeleri*	1
	Hentzia	palmarum	8
	Maevia	inclemens	1
	Marpissa	pikei	1
	Neon	nellii	1
	Pelegrina	proterva	2
	Phidippus	clarus	1
	Zygoballus	rufipes	5
Tetragnathidae	Leucauge	venusta	10
	Tetragnatha	caudata	1
	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	1
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	2
	Crustulina	sticta	1
	Dipoena	nigra	1
	Euryopis	funebri	3
	Latrodectus	variolus	9
	No id	Sp. TB	1
	No id	Sp. TC	5
	Phoroncidia	americana*	1
	Robertus	frontatus	1
	Steatoda	borealis	1
	Takayus	lyricus	2
	Theridion	albidum	2
	Thymoites	unimaculatus	2
	Tidarren	Sp. TA	2
	Wamba	congener*	1
Thomisidae	Misumenoides	formosipes	6
	Xysticus	ferox	1
	Xysticus	funestus	4
	Xysticus	luctans	1

Appendix E

* indicates species not caught on Nantucket

Muskeget Island

32 species, 3 unidentified, 13 singletons

126 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	2
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	1
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	18
	Araneus	trifolium	1
	Argiope	trifasciata	1
	Eustala	emertoni	1
	Neoscona	arabesca	8
Clubionidae	Clubiona	pikei	8
Corinnidae	Phruronellus	formica	8
Gnaphosidae	Zelotes	hentzi	1
Linyphiidae	Ceratinopsis	sp. A	1
	Grammonota	inornata	2
	Grammonota	sp. C	1
	Hypselistes	florens	3
	No id	sp. AE	2
Lycosidae	Arctosa	littoralis	7
	Pirata	insularis	2
	Schizocosa	avida	1
	Trochosa	terricola	1
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	1
	Tibellus	oblongus	4
Pholcidae	Pholcus	phalangioides	15
Salticidae	Hentzia	palmarum	4
	Pelegrina	galathea	1
	Salticus	scenicus*	1
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	caudata	10
	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	6
	Tetragnatha	vermiformis	2
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	7
Thomisidae	Misumenoides	formosipes	3
	Xysticus	ferox	1
	Xysticus	triguttatus	2

Appendix F

The Creeks NBI Plot

13 species, 1 unidentified, 11 singletons

19 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Araneidae	Cyclosa	conica	1
Dictynidae	Emblyna	annulipes	1
	Emblyna	cruciata	6
	Sergiolus	minutus	1
Gnaphosidae	Sergiolus	minutus	1
Linyphiidae	Erigone	sp. A	1
Lycosidae	Arctosa	emertoni	1
	Pardosa	floridana	2
	Pirata	sedentarius	1
	Tibellus	oblongus	1
Philodromidae	Tibellus	oblongus	1
Salticidae	Hentzia	palmarum	1
	Phidippus	whitmanii	1
Theridiidae	Euryopis	funnebris	1
	Theridion	murarium	1

Appendix G

Eel Point 2 NBI Plot

25 species, 2 unidentified, 11 singletons

97 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	3
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	1
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	8
	Araneus	thaddeus	1
	Neoscona	arabesca	5
	No id	sp. A	1
	Clubionidae	Clubiona	abbotii
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	1
	Phruronellus	formica	1
	Scotinella	divesta	1
Dictynidae	Lathys	pallida	7
Gnaphosidae	Zelotes	hentzi	3
Linyphiidae	Hypselistes	florens	2
Lycosidae	Allocosa	funerea	1
	Geolycosa	pikei	24
	Pardosa	sp. A	2
	Pardosa	saxatilis	10
	Schizocosa	avida	7
Philodromidae	Tibellus	oblongus	5
Salticidae	Hentzia	palmarum	4
	Phidippus	clarus	1
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	1
Theridiidae	Steatoda	albomaculata	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	conspurcata	1
	Xysticus	ferox	2

Appendix H

Madequecham NBI Plot

68 species, 16 unidentified, 38 singletons

218 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	2
	Agelenopsis	potteri	2
Araneidae	Araneus	bivittatus	1
	Araneus	thaddeus	1
	Araneus	trifolium	1
	Neoscona	arabesca	33
Clubionidae	Clubiona	kastoni	1
	Elaver	excepta	4
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	1
	Phrurolithus	similis	2
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	7
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	1
Dictynidae	Cicurina	arcuata	1
Gnaphosidae	Callilepis	pluto	1
	Zelotes	duplex	9
	Zelotes	fratis	1
	Zelotes	hentzi	1
Linyphiidae	Ceraticelus	alticeps	1
	Grammonota	sp. A	1
	Grammonota	pictilis	1
	Hypselistes	florens	6
	Macrargus	multesimus	2
	Maso	sp. A	2
	No id	sp. AA	1
	No id	sp. AB	1
	No id	sp. AC	1
	No id	sp. AD	2
	No id	sp. C	1
	No id	sp. D	4
	No id	sp. S	2
	No id	sp. W	1
No id	sp. Y	1	
Liocranidae	Agroeca	pratensis	1
Lycosidae	Arctosa	rubicunda	1
	Hogna	frondicola	9
	Pardosa	moesta	15
	Pardosa	sp. A	3
	Schizocosa	avida	1
	Schizocosa	sp. B	1
	Trabeops	aurantiacus	18
	Trebacosa	marxi	3
	Trochosa	terricola	2
	Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus
Oxyopes		scalaris	9

Philodromidae	Philodromus	placidus	1
	Thanatus	formicinus	1
Salticidae	Hentzia	palmarum	6
	Maevia	inclemens	1
	No id	sp. D	4
	Pelegrina	proterva	3
	Phidippus	clarus	3
Tetragnathidae	Leucauge	venusta	1
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	globosa	1
	Emertonella	emertoni	1
	Emertonella	gertschi	6
	Euryopsis	funebri	3
	No id	sp. L	1
	No id	sp. O	1
	Robertus	pumulis	1
	Steatoda	americana	2
	Takayus	lyricus	1
	Theridion	differens	1
	Wamba	crispulus	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	conspurcata	13
	Xysticus	ferox	2
	Xysticus	fraternus	2
	Xysticus	funestus	1
	Xysticus	luctans	1

Appendix I

Massachusetts Audubon Society NBI Plot

53 species, 3 unidentified, 26 singletons

180 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	4
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	2
	Araneus	alboventris	1
	Araneus	bivittatus	1
	Argiope	aurantia	7
	Argiope	trifasciata	19
	Cyclosa	turbinata	1
	Eustala	anastera	10
	Neoscona	arabesca	16
	No id	sp. A	3
	Clubionidae	Clubiona	abbotii
Elaver		excepta	1
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	1
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	1
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	3
Gnaphosidae	Phrurotimpus	minutus	1
	Cesonia	bilineata	1
	Drassodes	neglectus	1
	Drassyllus	creolus	2
	Haplodrassus	signifer	5
	Nodocion	eclecticus	1
	Zelotes	duplex	1
	Zelotes	hentzi	1
	Zelotes	laccus	1
	Linyphiidae	Grammonota	capitata
No id		sp. K	1
No id		sp. W	1
No id		sp. X	1
Pocadicnemis		americana	2
Lycosidae	Walckenaeria	digitata	1
	Hogna	frondicola	8
	Pardosa	distincta	9
	Pardosa	saxatilis	3
	Rabidosa	punctulata	1
	Rabidosa	rabida	5
	Schizocosa	avida	24
	Schizocosa	bilineata	4
	Varacosa	shenandoa	1
	Philodromidae	Philodromus	placidus
Thanatus		formicinus	2
Salticidae	Hentzia	palmarum	2
	Maevia	inclemens	3
	Phidippus	cardinalis	1
	Phidippus	clarus	2

Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	4
Theridiidae	Emertonella	gertschi	1
	Euryopis	funebri	3
	Theonoe	stridula	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	conspurcata	3
	Xysticus	bicuspis	1
	Xysticus	ferox	2
	Xysticus	gulosus	3
	Xysticus	pellax	1

Appendix J

Sheep Pond NBI Plot

51 species, 9 unidentified, 32 singletons

124 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	3
	Agelenopsis	potteri	1
Araneidae	Araneus	miniatus	1
	Araneus	partitus	1
	Araneus	pratensis	1
	Eustala	anastera	1
	Neoscona	arabesca	39
	No id	sp. A	1
Clubionidae	Elaver	excepta	2
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	1
	Castianeira	trilineata	2
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	1
	Scotinella	minnetonka	1
	Scotinella	pugnata	1
Gnaphosidae	Drassyllus	sp. B	1
	Haplodrassus	signifer	1
	Zelotes	duplex	4
	Zelotes	fratis	1
	Zelotes	hentzi	1
Linyphiidae	Agyneta	sp. A	3
	Bathyphantes	pallidus	7
	Florinda	coccinea	2
	Hypselistes	florens	1
	Macrargus	multesimus	2
	Maso	sp. B	2
	No id	sp. P	1
	No id	sp. R	1
	No id	sp. X	3
Lycosidae	Hogna	frondicola	3
	Pardosa	distincta	5
	Rabidosa	rabida	1
	Schizocosa	bilineata	1
	Trabeops	aurantiacus	2
	Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus
Philodromidae	Philodromus	placidus	3
	Salticidae	Eris	militaris
Neon		nellii	1
Pelegrina		proterva	1
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	2
Theridiidae	Euryopis	funebri	1
	Euryopis	gertschi	1
	No id	sp. B	3
	No id	sp. N	1
	Takayus	lyricus	1

	Theridion	albidum	1
	Theridion	differens	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana	1
	Ozyptila	conspurcata	3
	Tmarus	rubromaculatus	1
	Xysticus	funestus	1
	Xysticus	pellax	1

Appendix K

SHCP NBI

Plot

69 species, 8 unidentified, 25 singletons

443 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens	
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	9	
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	4	
	Araneus	miniatus	1	
	Cyclosa	conica	1	
	Larinia	borealis	1	
	Neoscona	arabesca	9	
Clubionidae	Clubiona	johnsoni	16	
	Clubiona	Morpho sp. A	6	
	Clubiona	pikei	3	
	Elaver	excepta	1	
Corinnidae	Meriola	decepta	1	
	Phrurolithus	similis	8	
	Phruronellus	formica	3	
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	4	
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	3	
	Phrurotimpus	minutus	10	
Dictynidae	Emblyna	cruciata	1	
	Scotolathys	pallidus	4	
Gnaphosidae	Cesonia	bilineata	4	
	Drassyllus	creolus	10	
	Haplodrassus	signifer	21	
	Micaria	longispina	2	
	Zelotes	hentzi	7	
	Zelotes	laccus	32	
	Linyphiidae	Agyneta	Morpho sp. B	3
Ceraticelus		bryantae	1	
Ceratinops		crenatus	1	
Ceratinopsis		atolma	1	
Grammonota		capitata	1	
Grammonota		pictilis	1	
Masoncus		arienus	1	
Neriene		clathrata	7	
No id		Morpho sp. BA	1	
No id		Morpho sp. BB	1	
No id		Morpho sp. BC	1	
No id		Morpho sp. XX	3	
No id		Morpho sp. ZZ	1	
Liocranidae		Agroeca	pratensis	1
Lycosidae		Hogna	helluo	5

	Pardosa	distincta	45
	Pardosa	saxatilis	55
	Rabidosa	rabida	3
	Schizocosa	avida	3
	Schizocosa	bilineata	8
	Schizocosa	saltatrix	1
Miturgidae	Cheiracanthium	inclusum	6
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus	5
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	1
	Philodromus	placidus	1
	Thanatus	formicinus	6
	Tibellus	oblongus	5
Salticidae	Habronattus	decorus	1
	Habronattus	viridipes	2
	Hentzia	palmarum	9
	Marpissa	lineata	4
	Pelegrina	galathea	5
	Talavera	minuta	3
	Zygoballus	rufipes	1
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	9
Theridiidae	Emertonella	gertschi	1
	Euryopis	gertschi	23
	Euryopis	Morpho sp. A	1
	Theridion	differens	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana	14
	Xysticus	alboniger	3
	Xysticus	bicuspis	5
	Xysticus	ferox	19
	Xysticus	funestus	2
	Xysticus	luctans	11

Appendix L

Squam Swamp NBI Plot
 50 Species, 8 unidentified, 20 singletons
 172 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	potteri	1
Araneidae	Mangora	maculata	4
	Micrathena	sagittata	11
	Neoscona	arabesca	2
	No id	sp. B	1
	No id	sp. C	4
Atypidae	Sphodros	niger	1
Clubionidae	Clubiona	abbotii	1
	Elaver	excepta	3
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	26
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	3
Dictynidae	Dictyna	sp. A	1
	Dictyna	sp. B	17
Gnaphosidae	Haplodrassus	signifer	1
	Sergiolus	decoratus	3
	Zelotes	duplex	5
	Zelotes	hentzi	1
Hahniidae	Neoantistea	agilis	2
Linyphiidae	Ceraticelus	alticeps	12
	Ceratinella	sp. A	1
	Macrargus	multesimus	1
	No id	sp. A	1
	No id	sp. S	1
	No id	sp. U	2
	Walckenaeria	atrotibialis	2
Lycosidae	Allocosa	funerea	4
	Hogna	frondicola	2
	Pardosa	distincta	7
	Pirata	insularis	5
	Schizocosa	bilineata	1
	Trebacosa	marxi	4
Salticidae	Eris	militaris	4
	Marpissa	lineata	1
	Pelegrina	proterva	5
	Zygoballus	rufipes	4
Tetragnathidae	Leucauge	venusta	4
	Tetragnatha	elongata	1
	Tetragnatha	versicolor	1
Theridiidae	Euryopsis	argentea	1
	Euryopsis	funebri	1
	Euryopsis	gertschi	2
	Steatoda	americana	2
	Takayus	lyricus	3
Theridion	albidum	3	

	Theridion	frondeum	1
	Thymoites	unimaculatus	2
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana	2
	Ozyptila	conspurcata	1
	Xysticus	ferox	1
	Xysticus	fraternus	3

Appendix M

Umass Field Station (Around the lab building)

32 species, 6 unidentified, 21 singletons

73 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni	1
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	1
Araneidae	Eustala	anastera	1
	Eustala	emertoni	1
Clubionidae	Clubiona	maritima	1
Dictynidae	Dictyna	sp. A	2
	Emblyna	cruciata	2
	No id	sp. A	1
Linyphiidae	No id	sp. BD	2
	No id	sp. BE	1
	No id	sp. BF	1
Lycosidae	Pardosa	floridana	2
Mimetidae	Mimetus	notius	1
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	1
	Philodromus	placidus	4
Salticidae	Admestina	tibialis	1
	Eris	militaris	1
	Habronattus	borealis	1
	Hentzia	palmarum	21
	Marpissa	pikei	1
	Pelegrina	proterva	1
	Zygoballus	rufipes	2
	Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	caudata
Tetragnatha		guatemalensis	1
Tetragnatha		laboriosa	2
Tetragnatha		seneca	1
Tetragnatha		viridis	10
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	2
	No id	sp. P	1
Thomisidae	Theridion	spirale	1
	Misumenops	asperatus	1
	Misumenops	oblongus	1

Appendix N

Species found on Nantucket Tuckernuck and Muskeget
that are not on Emerton's 1930 species list

133 species

Family	Genus	species
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	emertoni
	Agelenopsis	potteri
Amaurobiidae	Amaurobius	ferox
Anyphaenidae	Arachosia	cubana
Araneidae	Araneus	alboventris
	Araneus	bicentenarius
	Araneus	bivittatus
	Araneus	cornutus
	Araneus	diadematus
	Araneus	gadus
	Araneus	partitus
	Araneus	pratensis
	Araniella	displicata
	Cyclosa	conica
	Cyclosa	turbinata
	Eustala	emertoni
	Mangora	maculata
	Micrathena	sagittata
Atypidae	Sphodros	niger
Atypidae	Sphodros	rufipes
Clubionidae	Clubiona	johnsoni
	Clubiona	kastoni
	Clubiona	pikei
	Elaver	excepta
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa
	Castianeira	trilineata
	Meriola	decepta
	Phrurolithus	similis
	Phruronellus	formica
	Phrurotimpus	borealis
	Phrurotimpus	minutus
	Scotinella	divesta
	Scotinella	minnetonka
	Trachelas	pacificus
Dictynidae	Dictyna	formidolosa
	Emblyna	cruciata
	Lathys	pallida
	Scotolathys	pallidus
Gnaphosidae	Callilepis	pluto
	Drassodes	neglectus
	Drassodes	robinsoni
	Drassyllus	creolus
	Haplodrassus	signifer
	Micaria	longispina

	Nodocion	eclecticus
	Sergiolus	minutus
	Zelotes	duplex
	Zelotes	fratis
	Zelotes	hentzi
	Zelotes	laccus
Hahniidae	Hahnia	cinerea
Linyphiidae	Bathypantes	pallidus
	Bathypantes	reprobus
	Ceraticelus	bryantae
	Ceraticelus	silus
	Ceratinopsis	atolma
	Ceratinopsis	nigriceps
	Erigone	dentosa
	Florinda	coccinea
	Grammonota	maritima
	Hypselistes	florens
	Macrargus	multesimus
	Masoncus	arienus
	Pocadicnemis	americana
	Tennesseellum	formicum
	Walckenaeria	atrotibialis
	Walckenaeria	digitata
Lycosidae	Arctosa	emertoni
	Arctosa	rubicunda
	Hogna	aspera
	Pardosa	distincta
	Pardosa	floridana
	Pardosa	saxatilis
	Pirata	cantralli
	Pirata	insularis
	Pirata	sedentarius
	Rabidosa	punctulata
	Rabidosa	rabida
	Schizocosa	ocreata
	Schizocosa	saltatrix
	Trochosa	ruricola
	Varacosa	shenandoa
Mimetidae	Mimetus	notius
Miturgidae	Cheiracanthium	mildei
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus
Philodromidae	Thanatus	formicinus
	Tibellus	duttoni
Salticidae	Admestina	tibialis
	Admestina	wheeleri
	Habronattus	decorus
	Habronattus	viridipes
	Maevia	inclemens
	Maevia	vittata
	Marpissa	lineata

	Marpissa	pikei
	Pelegrina	flavipes
	Pelegrina	galathea
	Phidippus	audax
	Phidippus	whitmanii
	Salticus	scenicus
	Talavera	minuta
Scytodidae	Scytodes	thoracica
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	elongata
	Tetragnatha	guatemalensis
	Tetragnatha	seneca
	Tetragnatha	vermiformis
	Tetragnatha	versicolor
	Tetragnatha	viridis
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	globosa
	Argyrodes	trigonum
	Emertonella	emertoni
	Emertonella	gertschi
	Enoplognatha	ovata
	Euryopis	argentea
	Euryopis	funebri
	Euryopis	gertschi
	Latrodectus	mactans
	Latrodectus	variolus
	Phoroncidia	americana
	Robertus	frontatus
	Robertus	pumulis
	Steatoda	albomaculata
	Steatoda	americana
	Takayus	lyricus
	Theonoe	stridula
	Theridion	albidum
	Wamba	congener
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana
	Ozyptila	practicola
	Tmarus	rubromaculatus
	Xysticus	bicuspis
	Xysticus	fraternus
	Xysticus	pellax